

Oxidation of Sugars by Air in presence of Ceric Hydroxide Sol and Cerous Hydroxide Gels.

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The oxidation of carbohydrates, specially, simple hexoses, by molecular oxygen is a problem of great physiological importance. In strong alkaline medium, sugars are readily oxidised but within the range of p_H found in living organism, hexoses are very resistant to oxidation by air in absence of catalyst. Sphuer (*J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1494 ; 1926, 48, 236) has, however, shown that in presence of sodium ferro-pyrophosphate, glucose is slowly attacked by air. The mechanism of oxidation is based on alternate oxidation and reduction of ferrous ion. Dhar and co-workers (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 376, 799 ; 1926, 30, 939 *et seq.*) have studied the problem of oxidation of various carbohydrates and sugars by air. These oxidations were carried out in presence of certain freshly precipitated metallic hydroxides, *e.g* , cerous, ferrous and manganous hydroxides, etc. Two very striking conclusions were arrived at by them from

M—Mirror at 45° ; *B*—Manometer ; *R*—Temp. regulator ; *C*—Cell ; *T*—Thermometer ;
S—Point-o-lite lamp ; *L*—Lens ; *H*—Heater.

these experiments, namely, (i) all sugars are readily oxidised to CO_2 and H_2O by air directly in presence of these hydroxides ; and (ii) these hydroxides behave as simple inductors, the reaction between oxygen and glucose coming to an end when these have been completely oxidised.

No attempt has, however, been made to study the kinetics of these oxidations. It was felt that studies on the dynamics of heterogeneous oxidation processes in presence of catalysts might lead to an explanation of the mechanism of the reaction ; and in the present paper, results of such investigations are recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Apparatus.—The apparatus used in the present investigation is a modification of the Barcroft-Warburg apparatus for respiration. The nucleus of the whole apparatus consists of two glass vessels as shown in the diagram in p. 357. These reaction cells are provided with optically plane bases and are connected to simple manometers by a set of stop-cocks for introducing and evacuating gases. The cells are kept completely immersed in water in an electrically regulated thermostat which was shaken by means of wheels over parallel rails. The shaking ensures efficient stirring of the water of the thermostat and also a thorough mixing of air and reactant mixture inside the cells, which admittedly is essential for heterogeneous reactions. To investigate the effect of illumination, a window was cut out in the thermostat and sealed with a lens, at the focus of which remains a point-o-lite quartz mercury lamp. The reaction cell inside the thermostat was tightly held by a circular metal clamp and below it was fixed in the thermostat a glass mirror at an angle of 45° to the path of light. The parallel rays from the lens are reflected by the mirror and fall perpendicularly on the plane bottom of the reaction cell. The infra-red and ultraviolet radiations are cut off by transmission through water and glass. The whole arrangement is kept in a dark room. The mercury lamp is run at a constant current of 2.2 amp. from a storage battery of 30 volts. The absorbed radiation is determined by means of Moll thermopile and a Moll galvanometer. A NaCl solution coloured red with a dyestuff has been used as manometric liquid. The experimental arrangement is given in the diagram.

Oxidations have been carried out with the aid of (i) colloidal ceric hydroxide ; and (ii) freshly precipitated cerous hydroxide.

Oxidation of Glucose and Laevulose in presence of Ceric Hydroxide Sol.

In each experiment, a 15 c.c. mixture of the composition (5 c.c. of sugar solution, 5 c.c. of sol, 5 c.c. of dilute alkali) is introduced into the cell and the pressure-drop due to absorption of oxygen is noted from time to time in the manometer. A balance cell is also used containing all the solutions except sugar, serving as a thermo-barometer. The colloidal solution is extremely sensitive to any electrolyte and the use of any buffer solution is impossible. Very dilute alkali solutions are used for effecting variation of alkalinity. The pH value practically remained constant for a period of five hours which was the average duration of the experiment. For pH up to 9.6, no oxidation is observed during 5 hours in absence of the sol. The ceric hydroxide sol is prepared according to the method of Mata Prasad (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 153). The volume of oxygen absorbed at N. T. P. can be easily determined from the simple formula,

$$r = \frac{(V - v) \cdot x \cdot d_1 \cdot 1000 \times 273}{760 \times d_2 \times (273 + t)}$$

where, V denotes total capacity of the cell; v , volume of solution introduced; x , concentration of oxygen in the gas inside the cell; d_1 , density of manometer-liquid; d_2 , density of mercury; r , total pressure-drop in any given time; and t , temperature at which reaction is carried out.

One set of experimental observation is recorded in Table I to indicate how the velocity constants have been calculated.

TABLE I.
(In darkness)

Laevulose = 1 %. Conc. of sol = 0.016M (i.e., gram mol. of ceric hydroxide per litre in the state of suspension). $p_H = 6.6$. Temp. = 37.6. Rate of shaking = 45 times a min. Amplitude of oscillation = 9 inches.

Time.	Pressure-drop in Reaction cell.	Balance cell.	Total pressure- drop.	$r = \text{c. mm of O}_2$ = Pr. drop.	$K_o \times 10^2$.
30 min.	0	0	0	—	—
90	9	-1	10	130	—
150	20	4	16	208	0.0022
210	25	4	21	273	0.0019
270	35	8	27	351	0.0020
230	29	-4	33	429	0.0021
300	41	3	38	494	0.0020
					Mean 0.0020

TABLE II.
Oxidation of laevulose.

Shaking per min. 45 times	O ₂ conc.	pH.	Sol conc.	Conc. of laevulose.	$K_o \times 10^3$ in		Quantum yield.
					Dark.	Dark & light.	
	20%	8.6	0.016 M	0.33%	0.0085	0.0040	0.45
"	"	"	"	1	0.0086	0.0043	0.63
"	"	"	"	4	0.0036	0.0046	0.90
"	"	"	0.009 M	0.33	0.0027	0.0086	0.80
"	"	"	0.016	"	0.0035	0.0040	0.45
"	"	"	0.025	"	0.0039	0.0045	0.52
"	"	"	0.016	1	0.0036	0.0043	0.63
"	"	6.6	"	"	0.0020	0.0032	1.08
"	4%	8.6	0.016	"	0.0035	0.0088	0.30
"	20%	"	"	"	0.0036	0.0043	0.63
"	100%	"	"	"	0.0036	0.0042	0.54
45	20%	"	"	"	0.0036	0.0043	...
80	"	"	"	"	0.0047	...	...

The quantum yield has been worked out by assuming that the yellow ceric hydroxide sol absorbed the radiation having average wave-length $436 \mu\mu$. One such value is worked out below.

$$K_0 \text{ (light \& dark)} = 0.0043$$

$$K_0 \text{ (dark)} = 0.0036$$

$$K_0 \text{ for light only} = 0.0007 \cong 25 \text{ c. mm. of O}_2 \text{ per hr.}$$

$$= \frac{0.025 \times 2 \times 6 \times 10^{23}}{22400 \times 15 \times 60 \times 60} \text{ moles per sec. per c.c.}$$

$$= 25 \times 10^{12} \text{ mol. per sec. per c.c.}$$

Magnitude of light absorbed = 0.4 cm. (Moll)

$$= \frac{0.4 \times 900}{3.8} \text{ ergs, } \left[1 \text{ cm. (Moll)} = \frac{900}{3.8} \text{ ergs} \right].$$

No. of quanta absorbed per c. c. per second

$$= \frac{0.4 \times 900}{0.5 \times 3.8} \times 6.2 \times 10^{-27} \times \frac{3 \times 10^{10}}{436 \times 10^{-7}}$$

(Thickness of mixture = 0.5 cm.)

$$= 4 \times 10^{13}.$$

Hence quantum efficiency = $\frac{\text{No. of mol. transformed per sec. per c.c.}}{\text{No. of quanta absorbed per sec. per c.c.}}$

$$= \frac{25 \times 10^{12}}{4 \times 10^{13}} = 0.63 \text{ (approx.)}$$

Oxidation of glucose in the dark in presence of the same sol has been carried out in the same way. Results are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Rate of shaking = 60 times per min.

Temp.	O ₂ - conc.	pH.	Sol conc.	Sugar conc.	K ₀ × 10 ² .
32°	20%	7.7	0.025M	1%	0.0015
"	"	"	"	2	0.0014
"	"	"	"	4	0.0015
"	"	"	0.025	1	0.0015
"	"	"	0.016	"	0.0012
"	"	7.7	0.025	"	0.0015
"	"	8.8	"	"	0.0025
"	4%	7.7	"	"	0.0015
"	20%	"	"	"	0.00145
"	100%	"	"	"	0.0015
32°	20%	"	"	"	0.0015
42°	"	"	"	"	0.0023

DISCUSSION.

The reaction takes place on the surface of the colloid particles. The rate at which laevulose molecules strike the surface of the colloid is proportional to the free surface.

Rate of deposition = $K_1 S(I - \sigma)$ and the rate at which laevulose molecules leave the surface = $K_2 \sigma$, where S = total surface of colloid particles, and σ = portion of the surface covered by the sugar molecules. At equilibrium,

$$K_1 S(I - \sigma) = K_2 \sigma$$

$$\text{or, } \sigma = \frac{K_1 S}{K_2 + K_1 S}$$

where K_2 is small compared to $K_1 S$, σ is practically equal to unity, *i.e.*, whole of catalyst is covered by sugar molecules. The reaction velocity which is proportional to surface concentration is given as :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K, \quad \text{or, } K = x/t.$$

In other words, velocity will be zero-molecular. In the above experiments K_0 has been calculated in this way and found to be constant.

Absorption of laevulose molecules on the surface of colloid particles is almost instantaneous and the quantity absorbed is independent of the concentration of laevulose even up to very low concentration of laevulose. The value of K_0 has, therefore, been found to be independent of laevulose concentration. But variation in the amount of the catalyst is necessarily associated with variation of total surface and the velocity constant varies accordingly. This is shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Sol. conc.	Laevulose conc.	$K_0 \times 10^4$.
0.016 M	4%	0.0036
"	1	0.0036
"	0.33	0.0035
0.009	0.33	0.0027
0.016	"	0.0035
0.025	"	0.0039

The surface area S varies as $N \times A$, where N represents the number of colloid particles in the solution and A , surface area of each particle.

If the particles were of same size N would vary as the concentration. Hence K_0 should be proportional to concentration of the sol. The fact, that it is not so, indicates that the sol undergoes dispersion with dilution at constant rate of shaking. Exactly similar relations hold true in the oxidation of glucose in presence of the sol.

It will be noted that the velocity of reaction increases with increase in the rate of shaking which facilitates the interchange of oxygen between the liquid and the gas phase. As is to be expected, increment in the value of p_H also enhances the velocity of catalytic oxidation. The quantum efficiency varies from 0.5 to 1 under the conditions of our experiment.

Oxidation of Sugars by Air in presence of Cerous Hydroxide Gel.

Even at very low concentrations of alkali, glucose and laevulose were found to undergo oxidation by air, in presence of precipitated cerous hydroxide. The oxidations were carried out at p_H , 7.05, 7.09 and 8.6. Phosphate buffers were used in the former two cases and in the last, a suspension of $Mg(OH)_2$ freshly precipitated in a strong solution of $MgCl_2$ acted as a good buffer (Power, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 195). Reaction mixtures were made up as shown here.

Composition of mixtures.	Reaction cell.	Balance cell.
Cerous nitrate solution	5 c.c.	...
NaOH solution	5	...
Sugar solution	5	5 c.c.
Buffer solution	5	5
Water	...	10

The strength of NaOH used was just sufficient to precipitate the cerium completely as hydroxide. The volume of reaction mixture was always 20 c.c. and that of air enclosed in the cell was 132 c.c. nearly. The thickness of the layer of solution inside the cell never exceeded 0.7 cm.

It was, however, found that in absence of catalyst, the laevulose was slightly oxidised by air in phosphate buffers. This slow oxidation of laevulose has always been corrected for in the results presented in the paper. Table V indicates the amount of such oxidation.

TABLE V.

Laevulose = 1%. $p_H = 7.8$. Temp. = 37.6. Rate of shaking = 60 times per min.

Time.	Manometer reading in		Total pressure-drop.
	Reaction cell.	Balance cell.	
$t + 0$ min.	0	0	0
$t + 240$	10	6	4
$t + 300$	13	9	4
			—
			4 min.
			= 50 mm. of O_2

It is well known that when a gel of $Ce(OH)_3$ in water is exposed to air, it is slowly oxidised to ceric hydroxide, a pale greenish yellow solid. This ceric compound can be estimated by acidifying the mixture first with HCl and then adding KI followed by subsequent titration of iodine. Further if a warm solution of KI be added first and then the mixture is acidified, the same result is obtained. This fact has been verified experimentally.

When, however, cerous hydroxide undergoes oxidation in presence of sugars, an yellowish brown compound is formed which behaves in a different way from the pale yellow ceric hydroxide. This compound is quite unstable in presence of acids. It was found that if KI be added after acidifying this compound with HCl, practically no iodine is liberated, contrary to the behaviour of ceric hydroxide.

Job (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1900, 20, 207) and later on Wieland and co-workers (*Annalen*, 1929, 477, 32; 1930, 483, 217) have found that when H_2O_2 is added to a suspension of cerous hydroxide, a brown precipitate of ceric hydroperoxide is formed. In our experiments the brown precipitate obtained during the oxidation of sugars by air in presence of cerous hydroxide, was found to be identical with ceric

hydroperoxide. Ceric hydroxide and ceric hydroperoxide can be readily differentiated by iodine titration. While ceric hydroxide is stable in presence of HCl and can liberate iodine from KI, the ceric hydroperoxide is quite unstable in presence of HCl and can liberate iodine from KI only when KI is added before acidification. That the presence of sugars favours the formation of ceric hydroperoxide instead of ceric hydroxide is clearly proved by the experimental data in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

$\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_3 = 0.0955 \text{ g.}$ $\text{Temp.} = 37.6.$ $p = 7.9$ (phosphate),
Rate of shaking = 60 times per min.

Amount of sugar.	Time.	Thio. required when KI is added.	
		Before acidification.	After acidification.
Nil	130 min.	23.5 c.c.	23.3 c.c.
	190	31.0	30.8
0.005 g.	60	17.6	11.4
	300	31.7	21.6
0.05 g.	130	19.6	1.0
	310	21.5	Nil
0.1 g.	190	18.5	Nil

To indicate the procedure of following the relation, a detailed table of results for one experiment is given in Table VII. The summary of results for glucose and laevulose are recorded in Tables VIII and IX respectively. The figures in column 3 stand for total oxygen uptake with correction due to the lapse of 10 minutes between mixing the constituents and closing of manometer stop-cocks. Column 4 denotes the volumes of oxygen used up in the formation of ceric hydroperoxide as estimated iodometrically. K_s represents the constant rate of absorption of oxygen by the system after the first 70 minutes,

TABLE VII.

Glucose = 0.5%. $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_3 = 0.0478$ g. $\text{pH} = 8.6$. Temp. = 37.6.
Rate of shaking = 60 times per minute.

Time.	Total pressure drop.	Total O_2 uptake with corr.	O_2 uptake by $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_3$ to form hydroxide.	O_2 for glucose.	K_s .
1	2	3	4	5	6
10 min.	0	0 c. mm.	0 mm.	...	...
70	76	1153	1071	82 c.mm.	0.0405
180	91	1348	1120	228	—
190	106	1543	1167	376	0.0407
250	119	1712	1197	515	0.0403
310	180	1855	...	...	...
					0.0405

TABLE VIII.

Oxidation of glucose.

Rate of shaking per min.	Temp.	O_2 conc.	pH .	Amt. of $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_3$.	Conc. of glucose.	Total O_2 uptake at		$\text{O}_2 - \text{Ce}(\text{OH})_3$ at		K_s .
						70 min.	250 min.	70 min.	250 min.	
60	37.6°	20%	8.6	0.0478g.	1%	1062	1687	961	1081	0.0469
"	"	"	"	"	0.5	1153	1712	1071	1197	0.0405
"	"	"	"	"	0.25	1168	1753	1997	1298	0.0351
"	"	"	7.9	0.0239	0.25	137	384	127	148	0.0206
"	"	"	"	0.0478	"	394	914	387	489	0.0344
"	"	"	"	0.0955	"	1198	2186	1054	1460	0.0531
"	"	"	7.05	0.0478	"	349	739	290	371	0.0281
"	"	"	7.9	"	"	394	914	337	489	0.0344
"	"	"	8.6	"	"	1168	1753	1097	1298	0.0351
"	"	100	7.9	0.0955	"	1774	2801	1620	2058	0.0536
"	"	60	"	"	"	1380	2420	...	1740	0.0540
"	"	"	"	"	"	1198	2186	1054	1460	0.0531
"	"	20	"	"	"	1198	2186	1054	1460	0.0531
"	27.6°	"	"	"	"	910	1599	874	1348	0.0200
60	37.6°	"	"	"	"	1198	2186	1054	1460	0.0531
30	"	"	"	"	"	923	...	878	...	0.0406

TABLE IX.

		<i>Oxidation of laevulose.</i>						
Rate of shaking per min.	Temp.	Conc. of O ₂ .	pH.	Amount of Ce(OH) ₃ .	Conc. of laevulose.	Total O ₂ uptake at 2 hrs.	O ₂ = Ce(OH) ₃ at 2 hrs.	K _s (after 2 hrs.),
60 times	37.6°	20%	7.05	0.0955 g.	0.5%	1963	776	0.0552
"	"	"	"	"	0.25	2110	972	0.0446
"	"	"	"	"	0.125	1716	1107	0.0329
"	"	"	"	0.0955	0.25	2110	972	0.0446
"	"	"	"	0.0477	"	797	304	0.0375
"	"	"	"	0.0238	"	412	147	0.0306
"	"	"	7.05	0.0955	"	2110	972	0.0446
"	"	"	7.9	"	"	2782	1038	0.0570
"	"	"	8.6	"	"	3029	1263	0.0561
"	"	"	7.05	0.0477	"	797	304	0.0375
"	"	60	"	"	"	819	317	0.0364
"	"	100	"	"	"	832	324	0.0368
"	47.6	20	"	"	"	1023	351	0.0685
"	37.6	"	"	"	"	797	304	0.0375
"	"	"	"	"	"	797	304	0.0375
30 times	"	"	"	"	"	689	284	0.0270

In presence of visible radiations, the rate of absorption of oxygen increased some what, as shown in Table X.

TABLE X.

Temp. = 37.6°. Conc. of sugar = 0.25%. Conc. of O₂ = 20%.
Ce(OH)₃ = 0.0478 g.

Sugar.	Rate of shaking per min.	p _H .	K _s (dark).	K _s (dark and light.)
Glucose	80 times	7.9	0.0406	0.0487
Laevulose	60 times	7.05	0.0365	0.0420

Inhibition by glycine.—Dhar and collaborators (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 711) have shown that glycine is oxidised by air in presence of cerous hydroxide. But it was found in course of experiment that at a p_H as low as 7.9, glycine is quite indifferent to air in presence of Ce(OH)₃, at 32°. One such experiment is given below.

TABLE XI.

Temp = 32°. p_H = 7.9. t = 120 minutes.

Conc. of glycine.	Amount of Ce(OH) ₃ .	Total O ₂ absorbed.	O ₂ taken by Ce(OH) ₃ .	O ₂ taken by glycine.
1%	0.0478 g.	158	153	5 c. mm.
1	0.0478	160	154	6

Use of glycol buffers for the reactions was hence attempted. It was, however, found that oxidation of glucose is strongly retarded as shown in Table XII.

TABLE XII.

Conc. of glucose = 0.25%. Temp. = 37.6°. Amount of Ce(OH)₃ = 0.0478 g. Rate of shaking = 60 times per min.

Quantity of glycine.	p _H .	K _s .
Nil	7.9	0.0344
0.02 g.	8.0	0.0297

The yellow compound formed from Ce(OH)₃ was estimated in two ways by acidifying the mixture before and after addition of KI. The analysis of ceric compounds are given in Table XIII.

TABLE XIII.

Glycine = 0.02 g. Glucose = 0.25%. p_{H} = 8.0. $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_3 = 0.0478$ g.

Rate of Shaking = 60 times per min.

Time.	Thio. required when KI is added	
	After acidification.	Before acidification.
70 min.	3.0 c.c.	3.2 c.c.
130	3.0	3.2
190	3.0	3.2

It may therefore be concluded that in presence of glycine practically $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_3$ is formed and no ceric hydroperoxide can be detected.

DISCUSSION.

The oxidation of organic substances by oxygen with the aid of enzymes or inorganic catalysts has been pictured by Wieland as consisting of a preliminary process of dehydrogenation followed by the formation of hydrogen peroxide; and in some recent work of his school, cerous hydroxide in small quantities has been used for detecting the formation of hydrogen peroxide during the processes of enzymic oxidation.

In the experiments recorded above, cerous hydroxide not only serves as a detector for hydrogen peroxide produced during the course of aerobic oxidation, but its particles provided an active surface for the dehydrogenation of the sugars preliminary to the actual combination of the liberated H_2 with O_2 to form hydrogen peroxide. Similar properties are exhibited by oxidised platinum atoms present on the surface of platinum black catalysts.

Willstätter and Waldschmidt Leitz (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 119) maintain that "dass oxydiertes Platin und Palladium den Wasserstoff, den sie aufnehmen, in leichter dissozierbarer Bindung, in reaktionfähiger form, enthalten als Palladium und Platinhydrur." We may postulate that the chemical reaction can be represented by the following equations where SH_2 stands for the substrate sugar molecule.

At the beginning of the reaction, the entire catalytic surface is made of cerous hydroxide, and reactions (i) and (ii) proceed at a rapid rate. The nature of the catalytic surfaces changes as more and more of cerous hydroxide is converted into ceric hydroperoxide which is not capable of effecting the preliminary dehydrogenation of the substrate. After about an hour the reactions (iii) and (iv) balance each other, and the relative surface area of cerous hydroxide to ceric hydroperoxide attains practically constant values. Thereafter we meet with a steady rate for the absorption of oxygen which is the difference between the rate of absorption of oxygen to form hydrogen peroxide and the rate of decomposition of ceric hydroperoxide. Table VII shows that the amount of ceric hydroperoxide present in the catalytic system attains 90% of its equilibrium value in 70 minutes and full equilibrium value in about 300 minutes. The rate of absorption of oxygen when this stationary condition is practically reached is given in last columns of tables VII, VIII, IX.

It is clear from table XII that glycine is a powerful inhibitor of the preliminary dehydrogenation by the cerous hydroxide catalyst and the subsequent formation of peroxide. Dhar has always emphasised the point of view that the oxidation of carbohydrates is retarded by the presence of fats and proteins. Willstire (*Z. Physiol.*, 1931, 72, 88) has recently shown that the enzymic oxidation of adrenaline is very considerably delayed by the presence of amino-acids. Our investigation furnishes another illustration of the inhibition by amino-acids of the aerobic oxidation of sugars by inorganic catalysts.

The slightly catalytic action of illumination on aerobic oxidation in the present case is to be ascribed to the probable enhancement in the velocity of reaction (iv). This would ensure a larger relative ratio of the surface of cerous hydroxide to that of ceric hydroperoxide. Experiments to test this hypothesis are in progress.